

DIGI4 CIRCULAR

Digital platform for
data-driven and
physics-based product
development enabling a
circular economy

Digi4Circular is transforming the automotive industry with a digital platform designed for sustainable materials use. By combining material science, computational methods, and end-of-life processes, it ensures future car products are eco-friendly. The platform uses automated workflows and machine learning to optimize resources and reduce waste, focusing on lowering CO2 emissions and boosting recycling rates for a greener future.

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INFORMATION ABOUT DIGI4CIRCULAR!

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Project data

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WWW.DIGI4CIRCULAR.EU

Project partners

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